

“Development of an Artificial Neural Network based system for foreign exchange rate time-series prediction”

MSc Computing Dissertation

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Abstract

In this dissertation, an application has been developed for the implementation of an Artificial Neural Network based system for predicting foreign exchange rates. Research is presented which shows the nonlinear nature of the foreign exchange market. This leads into a discussion about suitable modelling tools with a focus on machine learning techniques. The Elman Recurring Neural Network is chosen as a candidate for the neural network model to be implemented due to its ability to record the internal state of the system and the potential benefits this might offer in time-series prediction.

A number of technical indicators familiar to traders have been implemented within the system and these can be combined with user defined neural network models to create a unique trading support tool. The class structure chosen is readily extensible making it easy for users to add new indicators as required. Performance evaluation measures and other statistical analysis tools have been implemented to analyse the predictions generated, helping to provide valuable feedback when optimising a models configuration. The actual and predicted results are also displayed in an interactive chart for the end-user to analyse in more detail.

Whilst the results of the neural network models implemented show only a low level of prediction capability, the framework provides a good starting point for further study and enhancement. This proof of concept development can easily be expanded upon further with additional neural network types added from WEKA libraries. Developed using freely available open source tools, it offers additional analytical capabilities for traders over other purely statistical packages, an easy to use alternative to specialist software or that which is cost prohibitive.

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1 Introduction

Ever since the first stock exchange was created in 1611 in Amsterdam, participants have sought ways to increase profitability and decrease risk. Many technical, fundamental and statistical methods have been created and implemented with varying degrees of success. No one method (of those in the public domain at least) has proven to be consistently profitable over the long term. As a result, research papers are published on a regular basis exploring the application of new ideas and techniques as the search continues for the *'holy grail of trading'*.

In this project a large number of papers on topics from behavioural finance to machine learning and chaos theory have been surveyed. A subset of the ideas and techniques from machine learning have been explored further and developed into an application for the prediction of foreign exchange rate time-series. As such, this dissertation is a constructive one, focusing on the design and implementation of a system.

The report is organised into six main sections; Introduction, Background Research, Methodology, System Implementation, Model Testing and Results, finally I conclude with a critical analysis of the work undertaken and an outline for possible future work and improvements.

1.1 Personal Motivation

I have always been interested in trading and for the last 5 years have traded my own account with some success. Having studied for my MSc in Computing, I have taken the opportunity to combine my passion for trading with my new technical skills acquired throughout the course. Instead of just using the knowledge I already have about Java and SQL, I wanted to expand upon it and stretch my skills further. I have also had a novice interest in artificial intelligence and a project such as this gives me the vehicle to pursue all three of these aspects. Given that I only had one semester worth of programming classes, I knew there would be a limit to what I could deliver in the time constraints and that I would have a lot more to learn over the coming weeks and months. To help mitigate this risk, I started work on development early in the second semester and also used a number of freely available tools and tutorials to speed up both the learning and development cycles.

At no point throughout the course of this project have I had the expectation that the work I was undertaking would result in finding anything truly profitable or groundbreaking. Instead my main motivation has been pedagogical in nature, pursuing the expansion of my own knowledge and skills.

1.2 Outline of the problem

Existing neural network based trading systems available on the market can be cost prohibitive for the beginning trader to justify purchasing unless they are well capitalised. Also, given the high failure rate (some estimates say up to 90% within the first two years of trading, but no reliable publicly available sources were found) for new traders starting out on their trading career, every effort should be taken to minimise overhead costs. As a result, the system developed in this project uses only freely available tools and software, combining them into an easy to use system for the analysis of time-series using neural networks, statistical measures and technical analysis indicators.

1.3 Objectives of the dissertation

- Expand Java knowledge beyond the first semester course and learn about additional development tools and techniques.
- Learn about machine learning techniques and the implementation of neural networks.
- Develop a java based proof of concept application for the analysis of foreign exchange rate time-series for multiple currency pairs and time periods.
- Develop a set of basic technical analysis indicators for use by the neural network.
- Provide statistical analysis of the results of different neural network models in order to allow the best performing ones to be refined further.
- Test whether providing a neural network with some typical technical analysis indicators creates better predictions.

2 Background Research

2.1 Can we really *'beat the market'*?

The field of trading systems and neural networks has been an active research area for well over twenty years with many thousands of papers being produced on the topic. The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) proposes that any opportunities for profit discovered by this research would be quickly arbitrated away as soon as the new theory or technique becomes public, thereby eliminating the opportunity. As a result, any system would cease to be profitable and the only gains expected would be in-line with the average market movement of the instrument being traded. Another argument against trying to predict the stock market is the Random Walk Hypothesis (RWH). Closely related to the EMH, this states that predictions as to future movements of a stock cannot be made on the basis of past movements.

Despite these objections, a number of research papers contend that the stock market and other complex systems are chaotic in nature. The movements of a currency pair or stock price only appear random as they are the result of a nonlinear deterministic process not readily captured by a model.

2.2 Overview of the Foreign Exchange Market

The foreign exchange market is the largest market place in the world with an average daily turnover of over US\$6 trillion globally. Given the size of the market, the number of factors which can influence the strength of one currency relative to another and the volatility of currency pair values; it has been shown that exchange rates are nonlinearly correlated [1]. As a result, many nonlinear parametric models have been used in an attempt to model exchange rates including chaotic dynamic systems and autoregressive models [2], [3], [4], [5]. Other nonparametric models have also been proposed [6] but showed no improvements over methods using the random walk model in out-of-sample testing. The main limitations of both the parametric and nonparametric models are that whilst they performed well in some cases, there are not general enough to provide consistent returns over time and thus could not be used to actively trade with. This has lead researchers to look towards some of the nonlinear models available within artificial intelligence.

2.3 Machine Learning

In addition to the statistical modelling methods above, there are a number of machine learning theories that can be used to model nonlinear systems. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been proven to be effective in situations which are complex, noisy and where there is uncertainty about the relevancy of certain parts of the data set being analysed (i.e. the relative importance of one piece of data over another). The main types of problem where they can be applied successfully are:

- **Function approximation** - selecting a function from a known set of functions which closely approximates the behaviour of the target function.
- **Association** - mapping inputs to outputs, used extensively in pattern recognition.
- **Pattern classification** - used in speech and handwriting recognition, natural language processing etc.
- **Time-series prediction** - using previous values to create models of time-series to predict future values

ANN's require no *a priori* assumptions about the scenario being modelled, a big advantage over the other model-based approaches described earlier. They are also nonlinear and can generalise making them particularly well suited for use in analysing the foreign exchange market.

2.3.1 Origins of Artificial Neural Networks

Motivated from wanting to understand how neurons in the brain might function, a proposal for an artificial neuron was put forward in [7]. They are an over simplification of a real neuron as found in the human brain, but the abstract model provided a starting point for further investigation. Instead of trying to model each mechanism involved within the neuron, the model only focuses on the information processing perspective. At its most simplistic level, a neuron can be thought of as comprising the following three parts; *dendrites*, *nucleus* and *axon*. The dendrites provide the inputs into the nucleus which then produces an output which flows down the axon and ultimately end up as electrical impulses to dendrites of other neurons (as shown in figure 1 on the next page).

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is a network of these neurons based on a simplified model of a human neuron.

We can model the dendrites as the inputs (x_i), the nucleus (or cell body) as the Sum and Transfer Function and the axon (or neuronal output) as the y . Each of the inputs (x_i) in figure 2 is assigned a weight (w_i), these are then added together and the resultant passed to the activation function.

Weights are used to adjust the relative importance of their corresponding inputs.

Figure 2 - Working principle of an artificial neuron

Depending on the threshold (also known as the bias) of the function, this will then either produce an output or not $y(x)$. This output can be either continuous or binary valued depending on the function used. Usually an output function is chosen that limits the value of y on the interval $[0,1]$ or $[-1,1]$. These models can then be connected together into a network, with more layers (known as hidden layers) and nodes added as necessary depending very much on the application area.

2.3.2 Mathematical Representation

The output of the artificial neuron shown in figure 2 can be represented mathematically as follows:

Where:

- $x_i(k)$ is the input value in time and goes from 0 to n ,
- $w_i(k)$ is the weight value in time and goes from 0 to n ,
- b is bias,
- F is a transfer function,
- y is the output value in time.

In addition to input selection criteria and initial weights, one very important part of the model is the selection of transfer function.

2.3.3 Types of Activation Function

The activation function (or transfer functions) is a large contributory factor to the performance of the artificial neuron and different types are chosen for different application areas. Typically, they are one of the following:

- **Step function**
- **Linear functions**
- **Logistic Sigmoid**
- **Gaussian**

2.3.4 Types of Artificial Neural Networks

A number of different classes of ANN architectures have been applied in trading and in particular the prediction of foreign exchange rates. Broadly, these can be

generally classified into the following main types; *feed-forward*, *feedback*, *competitive* and *hybrid*. The most common is the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) [8] and this is probably due to it being the easiest to implement.

An MLP typically comprises of several layers of nodes (see figures 3 and 4 above). Both of the MLP's shown utilise the same principles from the example in figure 2, with weights and thresholds and are a simple interpretation of the standard input-output model. MLP's have been shown to have universal functional approximating capability [9] and can be used to model nonlinear functions. However, there is no general guidance on choosing the correct number of nodes and layers and thus it is a case of trial and error when looking to find the best architecture for a given application area. In [10] the authors discuss some possible ways of optimising network performance, with one of the main points being around the normalization of the data should be undertaken, but there is no consensus on how.

One limitation of MLP's and feed-forward networks in general as identified in [11] is that the mapping of inputs to outputs is static. To be able to model dynamic systems such as exchange rate forecasting, it is beneficial if the network has the ability to store internal states. This type of network is referred to as a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN).

2.3.5 Elman Recurrent Neural Networks

Elman Networks [12] are a simple yet powerful example of RNN's (the basic architecture is shown in figure 5 below). Elman networks are a generalisation of Jordan networks in which only one context unit is implemented [13].

Figure 5 - Elman Recurrent Neural Network (ERNN)

As you can see from figure 5, the ERNN is an MLP with a single hidden layer, the only difference being the addition of extra nodes known as context units. These context units store the output from the networks hidden layer nodes in a feedback loop. This feedback loop within the network is said to record the internal state of the system which acts as form of memory. This memory capability is important for the type of network needed for time-series prediction so that the network can adjust its predictions based on values fed back into it, hopefully increasing the accuracy of its predictions.

Another possible advantage of using Elman networks for trading systems is that an Elman unit could be used to aggregate something like the Exponential Moving Average (EMA) for a given periodicity (x). Instead of just using technical indicators as an input derived from the time-series itself, the Elman unit could automatically determine which x was the best choice and could dynamically adjust it. Other statistical measures and technical analysis indicators will also be implemented to see if any of these being used as inputs into the context nodes improve performance.

2.4 Trending vs. Range-Bound Concept

The initial hypothesis behind this project was to segregate the time-series data for a given currency pair into three parts; *trending* data, *range-bound* data and *indeterminate* state data. The segregation would be conducted using technical analysis indicators, applied retrospectively, to identify which state the currency pair was currently trading in.

Figure 6 - Trending and range bound conditions

In figure 6 above, a simplified chart showing the exchange rate for a particular currency pair is plotted versus time. The chart has been divided up into three sections to show the different range-bound and trending states. In visual analysis of chart patterns like this, it is relatively straight forward to show where each of these different types of market conditions are located. It is much harder to do this in real-time predictively. There is also a level of subjectivity to the analysis undertaken and technical analysts will tend to differ on where the points of inflection between trending and range bound are. One proposal is to use a neural network model to provide faster non-lagging indicator to identify these different zones. This could then be used as an input into a trading system which would have different trading rules for each market condition. To do this, more than one neural network would be needed.

2.4.1 Combing Neural Networks

Using technical analysis rules, the time-series for a particular currency pair would be analysed to classify which data belonged to each of the three different market states. Once the segregation has been completed, three separate neural networks would be trained as follows; one with the range-bound data, one with trending data and the

final one would be the decider network which would be trained to recognise when the market was either; ranging, trending or neither.

As shown in above, the time-series data for a specific currency pair is fed into the

Figure 7 - High-level overview of neural network system

decider network which will then segregate the data for onward processing by the ranging and trending networks respectively. These will then pass their predictions to the trading system for action. Typically, different trading strategies are employed depending on whether the instrument being traded is ranging or trending. For example in a ranging market, if you are currently at the top of the range, it would be better to favour a short strategy than to enter a long position.

2.4.2 Limitations

One limitation of this approach is that under the Universal Approximation Theorem [8], a system of n (three in this case) networks used to model a time-series, can be represented as a single multilayer feed-forward network with a single hidden layer, therefore removing the need to have multiple networks. This theorem has also been proven to be true for neural networks using a sigmoid activation function [14]. In other words, it is better to spend development and testing resource on optimising a one network ANN than to build multiple networks, all of which would need individually optimising and testing.

Another implementation gap is that it is quite difficult to accurately segregate market data into separate data sets for trending and range-bound states. These trending and range-bound areas can change when looking at the data through different time intervals and appear to have fractal properties [15, 16]. Indeed, fractal scaling was demonstrated in an analysis of 21 currency pair's on a daily timeframe [17]. Short-

term interest rates and interest rate differentials also displayed some fractal characteristics. Given the fractal nature of market prices, trends and ranges have to be defined for a given resolution in time; this again adds more complexity to the model as multiple time periods would need to be used. For example, using data from 5 minute time intervals for a currency pair for a given period, the data might appear to be range bound, but in a 1 hour interval the price could be trending. Trading systems typically look for confluence across multiple timeframes. Having separate models for each timeframe would not be practical. There are many different time periods commonly used in technical analysis, testing for each one would be very complicated and potentially not produce any actionable results.

As a result of these limitations, a new approach was taken; an investigation into using technical analysis indicators combined with the underlying time-series as inputs in the neural network model.

2.5 Technical Analysis

2.5.1 Origins

Technical analysis, defined at as high-level as the study of price and volume, is widely used in trading to provide traders with a greater insight into patterns, trends and volatility. The earliest known use of technical analysis comes from 18th century Japan where traders (mostly famously Homma Munehisa) had been successfully applying Candlestick chart analysis to the study of rice prices [18]. This technique was later popularised in the United States by Steve Nison in [19] during the 1990's. The west was a little slower to catch on to this type of trading and the first example of technical analysis rules being developed were published over 150 years later than Munehisa's work in [20]. In this paper the author applied various statistical models (mostly those concerning activity similar to Brownian motion) to stock prices.

2.5.2 Criticism

Over the years many more indicators and models have been developed. One of the main assumptions behind the validity of technical analysis is that history tends to repeat itself and therefore if a particular level in a stock for example has been important in the past, it probably will be in the future. There is a lot of debate as to whether or not the indicators and techniques used provide any form of edge in the

markets. Under the weak form of the EMH, technical analysis is completely discounted. Despite this and other objections, technical indicators form a large part of most retail traders trading systems [21]. As a result, it has been argued that some of the widely used indicators can become a self-fulfilling prophecy. That is to say that, if enough traders follow the signals these indicators generate, their action alone might be enough to move prices in-line with the indicator. Another example relates to round numbers. As humans we have a tendency to simplify and one form of simplification is in the rounding of numbers to the nearest whole or fraction. Novice trades will use round numbers for stops and entry prices on their trades. These levels are predictable and market makers in particular will go “*stop hunting*” triggering trades for a small but highly predictable profit.

2.5.3 Use in this project

Following the findings in section 2.4, the three-neural-network concept has not been taken forward in this project. Instead, the use of more technical analysis indicators will be explored as supplementary inputs into the network model. For example, addition of the technical analysis indicator for Average Directional Index (ADX) [22] has been included as this is commonly used to give an indication of direction and strength of a trend. The ADX will be provided as an input back into the neural network and tested to see if it improves the predictions generated. A number of other standard technical analysis indicators have also been developed in the system and these are explained in further detail in section 4.7 and 5.3.

3 Methodology

In this section I discuss the project management, risk management, development methodology and software selected for use in the project.

3.1 Project Management

The plan I created for this project has largely been kept to and all deliverables have been delivered on schedule. The plan itself was kept at a high-level so that it was easy to manage and could review on one page. In addition to this plan I also kept a lower level task list which broke down the larger deliverables into smaller tasks each lasting no more than 4 hours (half a day’s work). Towards the end of the development phase, a number of the “nice to have” requirements had to be dropped in favour of additional testing time to increase the stability of the system and ensure that I had an adequate results set to demonstrate its functionality. I expand on these issues and more in the final part of this report.

3.2 Risk Management

In this section, I discuss the risks associated with completing my project successfully. The probability and impact scales below are based on Larson and Gray’s risk severity analysis in [23] and have been customized it to fit with the scenario of completing a dissertation project.

Table 1 - Risk Impact and Probability Scales

Impact Scale					
Objective	1 (Very low)	2 (Low)	3 (Medium)	4 (High)	5 (Very High)
Time	Insignificant time increase	<5% time increase	5-10% time increase	10-20% time increase	>20% time increase (no float remaining)
Scope	Scope decrease barely noticeable	Minor areas of scope affected	Major areas of scope affected	Could result in failure of dissertation	Will result in dissertation failure
Quality	Quality degradation barely noticeable	Only very demanding applications areas affected	Quality reduction requires supervisor approval	Quality unacceptable to supervisor	Quality of software will result in failure
Probability Scale					
	1 (Very low)	2 (Low)	3 (Medium)	4 (High)	5 (Very High)
	<10% chance of occurring	10-25% chance of occurring	25-50% chance of occurring	50-75% chance of occurring	>75% chance of occurring

3.2.1 Risk Descriptions and Scoring

The table below shows the top 10 risks identified after conducting a risk analysis of the project. For each risk, the phase has been included which shows when the risk is likely to occur (please see Appendix 8.1 for the Gantt chart). The columns *P* and *I* are for probability and impact respectively.

Table 2 - Risk Log

ID	Description	Phase	P	I
R01	Lack of technical knowledge about each of the components to be utilized in the system.	All	5	4
R02	System requirements not well defined significant rework needed in order to continue development.	Development	3	3
R03	Failure to deliver a working demonstration version of the system for the project presentation in July.	Initial Development	4	5
R04	Interfaces between parts of the system are difficult to establish and maintain.	Development	3	3
R05	Serious flaw found in concept and is unachievable within the given constraints.	Proposal, Interim	3	4
R06	Serious issue found with software towards the end of the project.	Dissertation	2	3
R07	Performance of system too slow and as a result fails to meet quality criteria.	Development	2	2
R08	Overlooking, forgetting or ignoring bugs in the system that directly impact performance and reliability factors.	Development	2	3
R09	Unexpected and/or unresolved bugs within libraries or other open source software used.	Development	3	2
R10	Data files are of low quality and contain errors (inaccuracies or omissions).	Proposal, Interim, Development	3	1

3.2.2 Risk Severity Matrix

The above risk analysis was then compiled into the following risk matrix.

Table 3 - Risk Severity Matrix

	5				R01	
	4					R03
	3	R10	R09	R02 R04	R05	
	2		R07	R06	R08	
	1					
		1	2	3	4	5

Key	Score
	High (Major risk)
	Medium (Moderate risk)
	Low (minor risk)

Impact

3.2.3 Contingency Actions Undertaken

In response to the risk analysis undertaken in 3.2.1, the following actions were completed in order to minimise the chances of the risk occurring.

Table 4 - Risk Mitigation and Contingency

ID	Mitigation	Contingency
R03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritization of tasks to ensure most important tasks completed first. • Design system so that a simple end-to-end working prototype can be achieved leaving more advanced features and GUI to later stages. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contingency time factored into plan, strategy here is avoidance.
R01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss feasibility and suitability of project with Java lecturer. • Reduce development complexity by using reliable stable tools and libraries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update requirements to be a better match to my skills as required and add time to plan for training, strategy is to reduce.
R02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use an iterative methodology to allow for changes in requirements to be easily factored into development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contingency time factored into plan, strategy here is avoidance.
R04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose stable technologies that have been proven to work well together with testimonials of previous project success. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contingency enacted and technologies selected that are known to integrate well (i.e. use of Hibernate for ORM), strategy here is avoidance.
R05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early engagement of project supervisor regarding the concept. • Thorough research as part of literature review to minimize the risk of pursuing a concept that isn't feasible within the given constraints. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 40 days of literature review time has been planned for to allow for extensive research, strategy here is reduction.

3.3 Development Methodology

An iterative development methodology was used for this project, breaking the complete build down into the following three stages:

3.3.1 Basic Framework

This part of the build was completed in time for the system demonstration at the beginning of July so that early results of the system, together with screenshots showing mock-ups of the user interface of the current build could be shown.

- **Setup of working environment** - building the database, generating the java models from the database and importing historic data.

- **Database schema and XML representations** - creating the database tables and java objects, testing the generated classes.
- **Integrating WEKA** - creating the database tables and java objects, testing the generated classes.
- **Basic performance metrics** - statistics and error measures.

3.3.2 Generalisation

The generalisation phase focused on data visualisation (charts), developing the user interface and adding functionality for selecting multiple different types of technical indicators, data files and other parameters.

- **Integration of JFreeCharts** - addition of charting functionality.
- **Development of GUI** - creating the database tables and java objects, testing the generated classes.
- **Transformers and technical indicators** - Expanding on the basic ETL functions and creating a library of additional technical indicators.

3.3.3 Optimisation and Results

This final phase of the development cycle was the most open ended and as a result the least efficient with regards to productivity. The high-level tasks for this phase were:

- **Miscellaneous improvements** - Refining the application to include additional features and updates to the GUI.
- **Model evaluation** - statistics and error measures, testing.
- **Results sets** – compiling results for inclusion in the final report.

At each phase of the development process, I made sure that the system continued to work end-to-end so that development would not go too far from plan. There was a significant amount of knowledge I needed to acquire in order to complete the final application, taking this iterative approach and focusing on the production of results limited the risk of not delivering something that worked. There are a number of features that I had wanted to add to the system (as discussed in section 6) in order to refine and generalise it further, but unfortunately these have had to be left for future work.

3.4 Software Selection

Given the objectives of this project, a healthy balance had to be found between stretching my skills and knowledge and setting out to do something which was either too complex or unachievable in the timeframe given. Because of this, the most sensible approach was to start off with the assumption that the application would be built predominantly using Java and MySQL (the two languages I had the most knowledge of). Open source tools, frameworks and libraries should be used if they meant that more functionality could be delivered in a faster with no impact on stability. In general, the principles followed when selecting software for this project were:

- **Free** – no cost, student edition or available as a trial version,
- **Supported** - Well supported and documented, ideally with a large active community,
- **Open source** – must be able to see the source code and be able to customise it if needed,
- **Training** - Good training materials available in many formats (books, online tutorials and video lectures),
- **Proven** - Each piece of software worked well (ideally providing synergies which would result in increased productivity).

After a few weeks of research and false starts, the following technology stack was designed as the basis for the applications development:

Table 5 - System Technology Stack

Each part of the stack is explained in more detail in the following section, with a discussion of alternatives and implementation issues.

4 System Implementation

Building on the technology stack discussed in the previous section, this part of the report details how each part of the system was configured and implemented including a discussion of alternatives.

As this is a research project with the goal of producing a *'proof of concept'* application with no live order execution or similar, Java was deemed suitable as the main development language. Java is widely used in finance, although for time critical trading applications C++ is usually the language of choice. Java also has a large number of useful tools and libraries available for development and is well supported by numerous community sites, books and other learning resources.

4.1 System Overview

The system has the following 4 high-level stages:

1. **Defining the data & import** – the currency pair, time interval (hourly, daily, weekly data etc.) and then browsing for the data file and importing
2. **Network configuration** - Setting up the configuration of the neural network (network type, number of nodes, epochs, momentum, specifying what to predict and other input parameters).
3. **Creating and training the model** – in this step an instance of the network is created and training and validation set parameters can be adjusted. The network is trained on a training set of data using the parameters defined in step 2.
4. **Reviewing the results** – Once the network is trained, the remainder of the data is used to validate and test the network. Statistics based on the performance of the network and a graphical display of the results.

4.2 Choice of IDE

Two of the most popular Integrated Development Environments available for Java are; NetBeans [24] and Eclipse [25]. Both would perform the tasks required of them for this project. NetBeans (version 7.1.2) was chosen as it's the one I'm most familiar

with and have used the most recently for other projects. (I also have Eclipse installed too as a backup.)

4.3 Data

One of the motivations for this project to be focused on the foreign exchange market instead of the stock market is the ease of access to relatively high quality data. Accessing historic data for various currency pairs is a lot easier than it is for stocks and other financial products. Brokers are very keen to attract new customers and therefore they are willing to offer simulation platforms with live data feeds and access to a large database of historic prices.

4.3.1 Selecting Currency Pairs

Based on an analysis of the volume data provided by each of the five major exchanges (London, NYC, Tokyo, Australia and Singapore) for April 2012, the most traded currency pairs in rank order were:

1. EURUSD
2. USDJPY
3. GBPUSD
4. AUDUSD
5. USDCHF
6. USDCAD
7. EURJPY
8. EURGBP

The top three pairs were selected for this study as they are the most actively traded and represent a global reach since they include Europe (via the Euro and British Pound), USA (via the dollar) and Asia (via the Japanese Yen).

4.3.2 Data Provider

The next step was to select a suitable data provider. In order to choose one, the following criteria were used to assess each option:

- Data quality,
- Ease of access,
- Speed of access,

- Customer support.

I approached a number of providers and two appeared to be viable options; Dukascopy [26] and Oanda [27]. Demonstration accounts were registered with both of them and within a couple of days I had access to a simulated trading platform. With Dukascopy, I was able to quickly download a large quantity of data for all the major currency pairs going back to 2002 for all possible time intervals. Oanda on the other hand required a manual data file request process to be completed with customer support tickets needing to be raised in order for their team to release the data. I completed the required tickets on 18th January 2012, the files were released to me on 17th July 2012, 6 months later. Needless to say, I had already decided to select Dukascopy as my main data provider.

4.3.3 Data Sets Used

Over the course of this project I have downloaded and used 82 data files totalling over 35 gigabytes, covering all the major pairs and time intervals.

My final data set (used for the results in this paper) contains 3.5 years' worth of data (from 01/01/2009 to 29/06/2012), for the EURUSD, GBPUSD and USDJPY currency pairs, for intervals of hourly, daily and weekly data. It is the spot price for the bid value for each time interval and includes the Open, High, Low and Close. Volume is also included in the files, but this data is meaningless to analytical purposes and is not used in this project.

4.3.4 Data Load Times

Initially I used very large data sets with varying levels of granularity, from tick data (the lowest) to weekly bars. The file import routine would typically process 5 records per second on average, meaning that a 3.5 year file with data for each minute took approximately 1 day 6 hours to import. Whilst initially it was interesting to experiment with such large granular sets of data, I soon lost interest waiting for the results. I did find a way to speed up the import routine by bypassing Hibernate, reducing the import time for the same file down to 110 seconds. However this was quite late in development and therefore wasn't implemented.

Table 6 - Number of Values for each Currency Pair by Time Interval (inc. Load Times)

	Hourly	Daily	Weekly
EURUSD	30,601	1,277	183
GBPUSD	30,601	1,277	183
USDJPY	30,601	1,277	183
Load Times	1hr 42min	4min	<1min

4.4 Database

Microsoft SQL Server was the first option that I looked at as I had used it extensively for a number of years in my previous job. However, I was keen to try something new and investigated the possibility of using MySQL instead. I downloaded and installed the MySQL Workbench and was impressed with the quality and ease of use of the product. After conducting a few more tests, I decided to use MySQL (version 5.5.24) [28] for the database. It has an optimised storage engine for fast read operations which is important in time critical tasks such as trading (even though my prototype wouldn't be time-critical). It is also open source and well supported.

MySQL Workbench (version 5.2.4) [29] was used to administer the database and execute any queries needed. This turned out to be an excellent tool and very user friendly. Below is the entity relationship diagram for the system. The initial design also included tables for the output of results from the network but this was no longer required once Hibernate was utilised as discussed in 4.5. WampServer (version 2.2) [30] is used as the database server.

Figure 8 - Entity Relationship Diagram

4.5 Object-Relation mapping

Object-Relational Mapping software is used to create an interface between relational databases and objects defined in an object orientated programming language. One key advantage of using this kind of software is that the all the database access calls are abstracted into Data Access Objects meaning SQL code does not have to be written directly within the Java classes. This reduces the overhead of maintaining the code should the database structure change as the object and relationship mappings will be kept in synchronisation with each other.

Hibernate [31] is one of the most popular frameworks for linking objects created in an object oriented programming language with the tables of a relational database. It uses JDBC to connect to a database and map the schema's relations to the Java object structure. It is freely available under the license GNU LGPL version 2 and an excellent tutorial can be found in [32] with a more extensive one in [33]. These tutorials were used in conjunction with the NetBeans guide [34] and the reference guide [35] extensively throughout the project. Another advantage of using such a framework like Hibernate is that it is database agnostic and can use many different servers (like MySQL, Postgres, MS SQL, Oracle, etc.) If at any stage during the project (or in subsequent work afterwards) the database backend needed to be changed, it would be possible to do so with relative ease.

Figure 9 - Data Access Class Diagram

4.6 WEKA

WEKA [36] offers a great variety of tools and the tutorial [37] on time-series analysis looked very promising. It is also well supported and has a number of neural network architectures implemented. In fact, WEKA offers a complete toolkit needed for developing a simple trading agent (i.e. data handling, network training and network evaluation). Given the abilities of WEKA and my early experiences working through the tutorial, it seemed to fit well with my requirements and would provide a good base on which to build.

For Elman networks however, I have had to implement this myself as they are not currently supported out of the box. There is an Elman function available as an extension developed by the WEKA community, available via Sourceforge.net [38]

and I added this to the weka.classifiers.functions class. This class was then been extended to integrate it within my application based on the guidance found within [39]. The Elman implementation is based on the code from within the WEKA library for an MLP, with changes made to reflect the architecture and initialization changes required as shown in the ElmanConfiguration class below. (The corresponding configuration panel is shown in section 4.1.4.)

Figure 10 - WEKA Integration Class Diagram

4.7 Graphical User Interface

The user interface during the prototype stage was read-only, i.e. without user input. Once the first build was completed and additional features added, a more attractive user interface was developed using the standard Java Swing libraries (see section 4.11 for more details).

4.8 Charting

Only freely available open source Java libraries were investigated and the top two that enjoy a good reputation and have had new releases during the last two years are:

- JFreeChart,
- JChart2D.

JChart2D is more lightweight while JFreeChart offers more gadgets, a wide range of different chart types and other features. Having found a very good tutorial [40] for JFreeChart, I decided to stick with it and that choice has worked out quite well on the most part.

Figure 11 - Charting Class Diagram

4.9 Technical Analysis Tools

The development of most technical analysis tools seems to have stopped (or at least decreased sharply) in recent years, potentially due to all demands being satisfied and most avenues of implementation completed. Due to the time required to include third party libraries (such as TA-Lib – <http://ta-lib.org>), I have chosen to use self-made indicators as long as:

- The required indicators are relatively easy to implement (e.g. moving averages etc.)
- A small number of indicators are required (<20)

As a result, within the data transformer class, I have defined a number of useful computations that can be used by the system as inputs or outputs into the neural network model when a new model is being defined. Some of the first technical analysis based trading systems used Simple Moving Average (SMA) based crossovers to generate trading signals. The effectiveness of these systems in recent years is limited as any opportunities they once provided have been arbitrated away. However, they are still widely used (specifically the 200 and 50 SMA) and may still be of some value to the neural network by smoothing out some of the noise in the signal. Exponential Moving Average (EMA) has also been included; this responds faster than the SMA and is usually used over a shorter time period (e.g. 14 days).

As part of my initial testing, I noticed that in periods of increasing volatility the networks predictions would get a lot worse. This led me to add a calculation for the Standard Deviation (SD) to the transformer class. The SD calculation is commonly used by traders as a measure of volatility. The idea being that this volatility measure can be used by the network which might be able to find a relationship in the data that makes the predictions a better fit.

A number of data transformation tools like EMA, SMA, subtraction/addition, shift operations, etc. and technical indicators such as Stochastic, Relative Strength Index, Williams R, ADX etc. have been included in the data transformer class. Some of these are used as technical analysis indicators and others (e.g. the shift operation) used in configuring the basic behaviour of the network (see section 4.11, stage 2).

4.10 Evaluation of Predictions

In order to compare different neural network models and model configurations a number of statistical measure and performance metrics were implemented. These are explained in detail in this section.

4.10.1 Statistical Analysis of Predictions

Statistical model evaluation and testing will mainly be performed through a couple of java utility classes. This could also have been implemented using some of the statistical analysis tools available as part of WEKA.

4.10.2 Performance metrics

A number of performance metrics have been used in the literature to assess the quality of predictions made by a system for time-series analyses. The three most commonly used in analyses of time-series model evaluation are; *Mean Squared Error*, *Normalized Mean Squared Error* and *Prediction Of Change In Direction*. In addition to these I have also included two other statistical measures; *Root Mean Square Error* and *Mean Absolute Error* which may or may not help evaluate the models created by the system.

4.10.2.1 Mean Squared Error

The most commonly used one is the Mean Squared Error (MSE), defined as follows:

Whilst the MSE can be useful in piloting the prediction model during the training phase, it is best used in conjunction with other measures if being used to compare the performance across a number of different models [41].

4.10.2.2 Normalized Mean Squared Error

A comparison against the Random Walk Model (RWM) (as discussed in the first section of this paper) is also typically applied to financial time-series forecasting. This measure is commonly known as the Normalized Mean Squared Error (NMSE) or U of Theil Statistic (THEIL) and is given by:

Where the results of the above can be evaluated as follows:

The closer the result from the THEIL calculation gets to zero, the better the model.

4.10.2.3 Prediction Of Change In Direction

Given that the types of time-series studied in this project are related to trading, where an ability to predict trends is of high importance, the POCID could be a useful evaluation measure. It provides a percentage figure for how correct the trend prediction of the model versus the expected value in the time-series. It is defined as follows:

Where the value of D_i is defined as:

4.10.2.4 Root Mean Square Error

The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) can be used as a measure of the differences between the target and output values of a system, providing a good indication of accuracy of the model and is defined as follows:

However, as discussed in [42], it is scale dependent and can therefore not be used to compare one model against another.

4.10.2.5 Mean Absolute Error

The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) can be used as a measure of the differences between the target and outputs values and is defined as follows:

4.11 System Walk Through (with screenshots)

In section 4.1, a high-level overview of the 4 stages of the system was discussed. In this section, the corresponding GUI components are explained in more detail with a brief user guide.

Stage 1 - Initial Set-up

Step 1 - Time Interval: Define a new time interval (e.g. Minutes, Hours, Days etc.) and the corresponding number of minutes in that time interval.

Step 2 - Currency Pairs: Create or delete a currency pair

Step 3 - Import CSV: Import data for the pair and interval created in steps 1 and 2. The output window in NetBeans provides a detailed log of each line of the CSV.

Parsing line: 14
Saving Rate: Pair: 5 - Interval: 14 - Date: Thu Mar 01 14:00:00 EET 2007
Parsing line: 15
Saving Rate: Pair: 5 - Interval: 14 - Date: Thu Mar 01 15:00:00 EET 2007
Parsing line: 16
Saving Rate: Pair: 5 - Interval: 14 - Date: Thu Mar 01 16:00:00 EET 2007

Stage 2 - Creating a Model

Step 1 - Basic Configuration: Configure the model to use the currency pair and interval defined in stage 1. Optionally specify the 'from' and 'to' dates (if Null is checked then the whole range of dates available within the file will be used). The

option to 'Exclude Weekends' is also recommended as any weekend data shown in the file will usually always be erroneous.

Step 2 - Defining the Outputs: Select each value (or transform) to be included in the model and click 'Add'.

In the dropdown list of values/transformations, the following options are available:

- **Open, High, Low, Close and Volume values** (class.ftsa.Data.Open, class.ftsa.Data.High, class.ftsa.Data.Low, class.ftsa.Data.Close, and class.ftsa.Data.Volume respectively)
- **Standard transformations**

- o **Stdev** - Standard Deviation of the “Parent” value for the last n days (n time intervals in more details),
- o **M** - Mean of the “Parent” value for the last n days,
- o **Slope** - Slope of the “Parent” value for the last n days,
- o **EMA** - Exponential Moving Average of the “Parent” value for the last n days,
- o **SMA** - Simple Moving Average of the “Parent” value for the last n days
- o **Difference** - Differentiates the parent value. (Ignore the “Days” value)
- o **Shifts** - Shifts the parent values by n time intervals positions (negative n means a past value and positive means a future value if available or Null if not available),
- o **Add/Subtract** - Adds or Subtracts the parent value to or from the Added or Subtracted value respectively,
- o **Technical Analysis Indicators** - RSI, WilliamsR, Stochastic, ADX.

Step 3 - Create WEKA Instances: After the inputs have been selected for inclusion in the model, the next step is to create the WEKA instances set. Select the ‘Instances’ tab and fill in the instances and press ‘Apply’.

Step 4 – Create WEKA Instances: Having created the instances, we then need to add its input values and the value we want to predict. As an example,

we will setup instances to predict the next close value using the latest two available close values as inputs. Press 'New' for each of the three inputs.

As these screenshots show, we now have 3 instances defined. The 'next value' instance is our predicted value and must therefore be defined as a 'Class Attribute'.

The final part of this step is to click 'Apply' in the bottom right and then 'Save'. It's very important that this is all done in the correct order otherwise unsaved instances will cause Hibernate errors and the model may become corrupted. If this happens, close the application and start again making sure to commit at each step. If this doesn't work, then the offending entry on the Instance table in the database can be removed.

Step 5 – Use Instances as inputs for an Elman Neural Network: Select the 'Neural Networks' tab, click 'new'; and choose the instances from the dropdown menu. This should be automatically populated with the instances created in the

previous step. Then complete the rest of neural network's initial parameters (these can also be modified later during the training stage). Click 'Apply' and 'Save'.

Stage 3 – Training a Model

Step 1 – Model Parameters: Select 'Neural Networks' from the 'model' menu, choose the neural network that is to be trained and fill out (or confirm) its parameters. Click 'Apply' then 'Train'.

Step 2 – Training Completed: After training is completed, the model will appear in the 'Training Results' list as shown below. (As with the CSV import routine, a log of the training progress is displayed in NetBeans).

Stage 4 – The Results

Step 1 – Review Predictions: The 'Predictions' tab shows the instance number, actual value, predicted value and error produced by the neural network. These results can be filtered using the radio buttons for the different data sets.

Step 2 – Review Performance: The 'Performance Measure' tab shows the performance indicators as discussed in section 4.10 (again these can be filtered for either full, training, validation or test sets).

Step 3 – Charts: The 'Chart' tab visualises the results of the training over all three sets.

5 Model Testing and Results

To recap previous sections, the following are available as parameters and data set options when looking to test and optimise the ERRN implemented within this project:

Data Set

- Three currency pairs (EURUSD, GBPUSD and USDJPY)
- Three different time intervals for each of the above (Hourly, Daily and Weekly)

Network parameters

- *Learning rate* (default = 0.100)
- *Normalization*
 - o *Normalizing attributes* (default = enabled)
 - o *Normalizing class* (default = enabled)
 - o *Normalizing to binary* (default = enabled)
 - o [Note - Based on the discussion of normalization in [10], all of the normalization parameters will be kept enabled throughout all tests.]
- *Decay* (default = disabled)
- *The number of hidden nodes* (default = 10)
- *Momentum* (default = 0)
- *The number of Epochs* (default = 100)
- *Size of training, validation and test sets* (currently hardcoded as .6, .3 and .1 respectively)

The most basic model implemented in this testing phase is the one used in the example from section 4.11; predicting the 'next value' from the current and 'previous values' using the sigmoid function. This is the basic model used in the first round of testing for each currency pair and time interval, using the default values.

5.1 Example Default Test Results

Table 7 - EURUSD Weekly 2 Values

EURUSD Weekly - Predicting S(C,1) based on C and S(C,C:-1)								
Learning rate	Epochs	HNodes	MSE	NMSE	RMSE	R2	MAE	POCID
0.1	100	10	0.00230	25.04306	0.04794	0.50987	0.03958	47.5
0.1	1000	10	0.0018	9.25051	0.04244	0.6157	0.03423	49.2

			0			7		
0.1	10000	10	0.0006 2	2.02729	0.02499	0.8667 8	0.02031	51.9
0.05	100	10	0.0010 9	8.42963	0.03308	0.7665 7	0.02732	48.6
0.05	1000	10	0.0006 7	2.21446	0.02580	0.8579 9	0.02096	45.3
0.05	10000	10	0.0005 2	1.21405	0.02275	0.8896 3	0.01807	51.9
0.05	100	15	0.0015 9	19.60723	0.03984	0.6615 2	0.03320	50.8
0.05	1000	15	0.0007 5	2.59305	0.02734	0.8405 6	0.02234	45.3
0.05	10000	15	0.0005 6	1.04749	0.02359	0.8812 8	0.01864	46.4
0.05	100	20	0.0026 5	83.03015	0.05144	0.4357 0	0.04274	49.2
0.05	1000	20	0.0008 2	2.95549	0.02857	0.8259 2	0.02344	45.9
0.05	10000	20	0.0005 5	1.13285	0.02352	0.8820 4	0.01873	47.5

The two key statistics here are the NMSE and POCID. As discussed earlier, a NSME of >1 means that the model performs worse than the Random Walk Model. A POCID of less than 50 means that the prediction of the trend is worse than a coin flip.

In another test using a similar model but with 5 previous values for C as inputs but this time for weekly data over the same period showed similar results. The only one with an NMSE of less than 1 is due to the fact that there are 20 nodes. This might have given a better prediction than a random walk, but it is likely just the result of over optimisation. Indeed on further analysis of the results set, the NMSE for the testing set is in fact 1.41 thus proving its performance was poor.

Table 8 - EURUSD Weekly 5 Values

EURUSD Weekly - Predicting S(C,1) based on C and S(C,C:-4)								
Learning rate	Epochs	Hidden Nodes	MSE	NMSE	RMSE	R2	MAE	POCID
0.1	100	10	0.00147	30.95016	0.03837	0.55751	0.03042	50.8
0.1	1000	10	0.00045	4.36801	0.02131	0.86348	0.01693	49.7
0.1	10000	10	0.00233	12.01791	0.04825	0.30030	0.03021	57.9
0.05	100	10	0.00075	13.32436	0.02738	0.77460	0.02181	47.0
0.05	1000	10	0.00026	2.10503	0.01623	0.92086	0.01283	49.7
0.05	10000	10	0.00046	4.00185	0.02135	0.86300	0.01491	53.6
0.05	100	15	0.00126	36.03927	0.03553	0.62055	0.02806	47.0
0.05	1000	15	0.00032	2.69026	0.01775	0.90526	0.01415	50.8

0.05	10000	15	0.00037	5.20428	0.01929	0.88820	0.01554	51.9
0.05	100	20	0.00195	68.89400	0.04416	0.41382	0.03467	48.1
0.05	1000	20	0.00035	2.90098	0.01878	0.89397	0.01487	49.7
0.05	10000	20	0.00023	0.82824	0.01508	0.93168	0.01191	49.2
0.05	10000	5	0.00053	4.00550	0.02297	0.84143	0.01792	49.7
0.05	10000	4	0.00053	3.78544	0.02295	0.84162	0.01736	51.4

Table 9 - EURUSD Hourly 5 Values

EURUSD Hourly - Predicting S(C,1) based on C and S(C,C:-4)								
Learning rate	Epochs	HNodes	MSE	NMSE	RMSE	R2	MAE	POCID
0.1	1000	10	0.00070	10.44559	0.02639	0.85456	0.02194	48.5
0.1	100	10	0.00240	216.04983	0.04902	0.49803	0.04117	48.5
0.05	100	10	0.00088	33.77719	0.02962	0.81673	0.02465	48.8
0.05	1000	10	0.00040	5.24319	0.01997	0.91670	0.01638	47.8
0.05	10000	10	0.00019	2.25370	0.01396	0.95929	0.01138	48.1
0.1	10000	10	0.00042	5.61454	0.02040	0.91309	0.01678	48.4
0.1	10000	15	0.00044	5.93731	0.02089	0.90884	0.01721	48.7
0.1	1000	15	0.00084	13.01123	0.02890	0.82555	0.02409	48.5
0.1	100	15	0.00427	2373.91043	0.06532	0.10857	0.05495	49.9
0.05	100	15	0.00160	122.91027	0.04004	0.66502	0.03361	48.9
0.05	1000	15	0.00051	7.07269	0.02250	0.89422	0.01867	48.1
0.05	10000	15	0.00022	2.48747	0.01473	0.95465	0.01202	48.4

The third and final test shown in table 9, was undertaken to try and see if a different time interval of data would respond better to this network configuration. The results are still poor with no significant improvements.

5.2 Analysis

The system behaves as designed for the tests undertaken above. More work is needed to create alternative models using the various inputs and technical indicators available. Additionally, the possibility of using genetic algorithms to set the model parameters could be explored to speed up the process of finding better models.

6 Conclusion

In reviewing my objectives for this project, I believe that overall it has been a success. As outlined in section 1, the main motivators for me were to combine three key criteria; to expand my Java knowledge, to learn about artificial intelligence techniques and to do both of these in an application area related to trading. I know that my Java knowledge has come on in leaps and bounds over the past 12 months. Using tools like Hibernate really helped to make the whole process of getting objects and a database to work in harmony much smoother. This is one of the main achievements I'm most excited about as being able to combine both OOP and DBMS seamlessly is when things start to get really interesting.

6.1 Summary of Achievements

- Successfully delivered a system that uses foreign exchange data for and currency pair and time interval to make predictions,
- Gained strong working knowledge of a number of new tools and techniques,
- Built up a good level of understanding of some machine learning theories,

6.2 Critical Appraisal

6.2.1 Research methods

I had a rather large wish list of things I wanted to explore and develop when I started this project. I originally wanted to develop not only a neural network system from scratch but also a trading system, with portfolio analysis, order execution, API calls to external brokerage platforms and more. Trying to do either of those two with no libraries or outside help would have been a sure path to failure. I wished I'd dropped the trading system from my scope much sooner as I spent countless hours reading through books and papers trying to create my own unique system based on how I trade. It was all getting a little too complicated and ultimately unachievable.

The same could also be true of my aspirations regarding what I could do with neural networks (one of which I outlined in section 2.4). There were many more other concepts that I erroneously explored. I think one core problem was I didn't have the fundamental theoretical grounding established in basic AI principles from which to build upon and expand. I pretty much jumped into the deep end and started trying to

bolt theories and concepts together as my prototype system developed. Ideally, I would have had 3 years of a BSc in Computer Science under my belt and a number of similar sized applications developed so I knew more about what I was letting myself in for.

Upon hindsight I tried to cover too large an area of research with insufficient background knowledge in some of the key concepts and theories. Instead of trying to learn new concepts, new software and new application areas all at the same time I should have just tried to learn one of those aspects and then work from there.

On a positive note, I read a lot of very interesting material and I know far more about the topics I explored than I did when I started.

6.2.2 Development methodology

The iterative approach I undertook was a sound one and focus my initial efforts on delivering a working prototype by the demonstration stage was a key part of delivering anything at all. I think I fell victim to the trap that you sometimes read in the literature where people mistake rapid/iterative development for unstructured or unfocused development. If anything, with an iterative approach you need to be more structured about how you approach the project. Because I was trying to build a system at the same time as build an understanding of what all the theories and concepts were, a fair amount of rework was needed which resulted in lost time. I also wished I had invested some time and effort into using some kind of source control/version system. I've lost count of how many times I had to rebuild all the Hibernate files and the database due to silly errors and changes I rolled out too quickly.

6.2.3 Professional development

From a professional development perspective, I certainly know a lot more about the hands on implementation issues you can face when developing software. Previously I'd only been expected to deliver on the project management and business analysis side of the process. The issues you typically face being a project manager are more likely to be people or process related and require a different set of skills to tackle. Now having had much more exposure to the development side, I can see that the issues faced can quite a bit different. You can't talk your way through an algorithm and expect it to suddenly change its mind and give you the right result. You have to

systematically breakdown the problem and follow each possible route through the process until slowly but surely clues start to immerge about where the real issue is and how you might be able to address it.

Although it disappoints me to say it, I think I've come to the realisation that I'm not cut out to be a professional developer. A hobbyist programmer sure, but I can't see it being something that I choose to make a career out of. However, the skills I've learned about attention to detail, testing and structuring an application are all readily transferable.

6.3 Further Work

Out of all other the things still on my wish list, the one I wish I had implemented was the addition of another type of network to test the ERRN against. A simple MLP would have sufficed, but I got side tracked in data issues and polishing the GUI. I would then be able to undertake much more testing to prove if my theory of using an ERRN with technical analysis indicators improved performance. I would also like to explore the use of Genetic Algorithms to help train the neural networks by finding the best configuration values. Doing this by hand was a long laborious process and not very successful.

I'd also still like to explore adding weights to different hours in the day to reflect the potential relative importance of the different trading sessions around the world. In particular I need to code ways to adjust for weights associated with the different sessions (Asia, Europe and US) as one of my theories is that price movements from different sessions should be considered more significant than others.

In parallel to these technical aspects, research was also undertaken into the integration of a simple trading system to model the order execution and position sizing elements of this project. In particular, the trading system design and development methodology developed by Robert Pardo from his book on trading system development as it offers an excellent framework for the complete process with excellent sections on testing and optimisation. However, this part of the system was deprioritised as getting the initial prototype working was taking longer than expected. I'd like to revisit this initial research to try and implement at least a very basic trading system.

7 Bibliography

- [1] H. Fang, K. S. Lai and M. Lai, "Fractal structure in currency futures price dynamics," *Journal of Futures Markets*, vol. 14, pp. 169-181, 1994.
- [2] D. A. Peel and P. Yadav, "The time series behaviour of spot exchange rates in the German hyper-inflation period: Was the process chaotic?" *Empirical Economics*, vol. 20, pp. 455-463, 1995.
- [3] T. Bollerslev, "Modelling the coherence in short-run nominal exchange rates: A multivariate generalized ARCH model," *Review of Economics and Statistics*, vol. 72, pp. 498-505, 1990.
- [4] D. A. Hsieh, "Modelling heteroscedasticity in daily foreign-exchange rates," *Journal of Business and Economic Statistics*, vol. 7, pp. 307–317, 1989.
- [5] M. K. P. So, K. Lam and W. K. Li, "Forecasting exchange rate volatility using autoregressive random variance model," *Applied Financial Economics*, vol. 9, pp. 583-591, 1999.
- [6] F. X. Diebold and J. A. Nason, "Nonparametric exchange rate prediction," *Journal of International Economics*, vol. 28, pp. 315-322, 1990.
- [6] W. S. McCulloch and W. H. Pitts, "A logical calculus of the ideas immanent in nervous activity", *Bulletin of Mathematical Biophysics*, vol. 5, 1943, pp. 115-133
- [7] D. E. Rumelhart, G. E. Hinto and R. J. Williams, "Learning internal representation by error propagation, in Parallel Distributed Processing," Ed. D. E. Rumelhart and J. L. McClelland, Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1986, pp. 318-362.
- [8] B. C. Csaji. "Approximation with Artificial Neural Network," Faculty of Sciences; Eotvos Loránd University, Hungary, 2001
- [9] G.B. Orr and K. Muller, "Neural Networks: tricks of the trade", Springer, 1998.
- [10] K. Doya, *Recurrent Networks: Learning Algorithms*, The Handbook of Brain Theory and Neural Networks, 2nd ed., Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2003, pp. 955-960.

- [11] J. Elman, "Finding structure in time," *Cognitive Science*, vol. 14, pp. 179-211, 1990.
- [12] M. I. Jordan, "Serial order: A Parallel Distributed Processing Approach," Institute of Cognitive Science, Tech. Rep. pp. 86-104, 1986.
- [13] G. Cybenko, "Approximations by superpositions of sigmoidal functions," *Mathematics of Control, Signals, and Systems*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 303-314, 1989.
- [14] B. B. Mandelbrot, "Fractals: Form, Chance, and Dimension", New York, Freeman, 1977.
- [15] B. B. Mandelbrot, "The Fractal Geometry of Nature", New York, Freeman, 1977.
- [16] G. R. Richards, "The fractal structure of exchange rates: measurement and forecasting", *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, vol 10, issue 2, June 2000, pp. 163-180
- [17] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Homma_Munehisa
- [18] *Candlestick Charting Explained: Timeless Techniques for Trading Stocks and Futures*, Gregory L. Morris, McGraw-Hill, 2006
- [19] Bachelier, L. (1900), *Theorie de la Speculation* (Thesis), *Annales Scientifiques de l'Ecole Normale Supérieure*, III -17, 21-86. (English Translation;- Cootner (ed.), (1964) *Random Character of Stock Market Prices*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology pp17-78 or Haberman S. and Sibbett T. A. (1995) (eds.), *History of Actuarial Science*, VII, 15-78. London)
- [20] Robert J. Van Eyden. *The Application of Neural Networks in the Forecasting of Share Prices*. Finance and Technology Publishing, 1996.
- [21] J. W. Wilder, "New Concepts in Technical Trading Systems", Greensboro, NC, Trend Research, 1978.
- [22] E. Larson and C. F. Gray, "Project Management: The Managerial Process," 5th ed. New York, NY: McGraw Hill, 2010.
- [23] <http://netbeans.org/>

- [24] <http://www.eclipse.org/>
- [25] <http://www.dukascopy.com/>
- [26] <http://www.oanda.com/>
- [27] <http://www.mysql.com/>
- [28] Workbench, <http://www.mysql.com/products/workbench/>
- [29] <http://www.wampserver.com>
- [30] <http://www.hibernate.org/>
- [31] <http://www.javapassion.com/handsonlabs/hibernatestepbystep>
- [32] “Hibernate Tutorial”, Hibernate Community Documentation
<http://docs.jboss.org/hibernate/core/3.3/reference/en/html/tutorial.html>
- [33] “Hibernate Tutorial”, NetBeans wiki, <http://wiki.netbeans.org/Hibernate>
- [34] “Hibernate Tools – Reference Guide”, Hibernate Community Documentation
http://docs.jboss.org/tools/2.1.0.Beta1/hibernatetools/html_single/
- [35] <http://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/~ml/weka/>
- [36] “Time Series Analysis and Forecasting with Weka”,
<http://wiki.pentaho.com/display/DATAMINING/Time+Series+Analysis+and+Forecasting+with+Weka>
- [37] <http://sourceforge.net/projects/wekann/>
- [38] S. Maheshwari and S. Joshi, “Extending WEKA Framework for Learning New Algorithms”, Technical Trends, CSI Communications, May 2012.
- [39] M. D’Andrea, “JFreeChart Tutorial”, http://www.if.pw.edu.pl/~ertman/pojava/?download=jfreechart_tutorial.pdf
- [40] Clements, M. P., & Hendry, D. F. (1993). On the limitations of comparing mean square forecast errors. *Journal of Forecasting*, 12(8), 617–637
- [41] Hyndman, Rob J. Koehler, Anne B. (2006). "Another look at measures of forecast accuracy". *International Journal of Forecasting*: 679-688.

8 Appendices

Note - Please see CD for all source code and supporting files

8.1 Final Gantt Chart

